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EXTERIOR TO WOMEN OF SURKHAN BAKSHI

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Abstract: In this article, Uzbek folk epics embody the long past, cultural life and national values of our ancestors, and this immortal, intangible cultural heritage of ours is highly valued even today. It is said that the beautiful performances of the Bakhshchik art bring great pleasure to the listeners and serve as a source of spiritual propaganda that invites people to do good, spreads enlightenment, and awakens good qualities in the hearts of the young generation. goes

Key words: Alpomish, Gorogli, Nurali, Khondali, Golden pumpkin, Momogul maston, Bulungur, Nurota, Narpay, Kamay, Kurgon, terma.

ЭКСТЕРЬЕР ДЛЯ ЖЕНЩИН СУРХАН БАХШИ

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Аннотация: В данной статье узбекские народные эпосы воплощают в себе давнее прошлое, культурную жизнь и национальные ценности наших предков, и это наше бессмертное, нематериальное культурное наследие высоко ценится и сегодня. Говорят, что прекрасные выступления бахшиковского искусства доставляют огромное удовольствие слушателям и служат источником духовной пропаганды, призывающей к добру, распространяющей просвещение, пробуждающей добрые качества в сердцах подрастающего поколения. идет

Ключевые слова: Алпомыш, Гёроглы, Нурали, Хондали, Золотая тыква, Момогуль мастон, Булунгур, Нурота, Нарпай, Камай, Кургон, терма.

The basis of the spiritual values of the Uzbek people is the traditional epic and the art of giving. That's why Uzbek folklore is extremely rich and always attractive to foreign tourists. The art of Bakhchik, which embodies our national values, is known worldwide today and is among the highest examples of art in the countries of the world. Art-loving peoples of the world are looking at the art of giving with great interest. Dozens of scientific research institutes regularly conduct practical work on the study of unique masterpieces of the art of

baksheesh. Bakhshchik art serves as an important mediator for bringing together international artists and establishing mutual cooperation between them. The activity of Bakhshchilik art, which has a worthy place among the highly developed arts of the world, was positively evaluated and included in the representative list of UNESCO's World Intangible Cultural Heritage. Thanks to the achievement of the independence of the Uzbek people, the art of philanthropy was revived and entered a stage of further development. In November 1999, the 1000th anniversary of the epic "Alpomish" was celebrated under the auspices of UNESCO. In 2000, the title of People's Bakhsh was established. In 2018, the "Bakhshish School" was established in the city of Termiz at the initiative of the Honorable President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev.

Uzbek folk epics embody the long past, cultural life and national values of our ancestors, and this immortal, intangible cultural heritage of ours is highly valued even today. The beautiful performances of Bakhshchik art bring great pleasure to the listeners, and serve as a source of spiritual propaganda that invites people to do good, spreads enlightenment, and awakens good qualities in the hearts of the young generation. Bakhshi is a talent who can sing epics and thermas and show his acting, poetry and musician skills at the same time. The role of the Surkhan oasis school of epics, which trains such talented people, is incomparable. In this school, well-known folk singers grow up, participate in folk festivals and entertainments, various family ceremonies, preserve and continue their performance styles. Bakhshini, who performed the song that embodies the epics, terms and sayings of the national folk oral creativity, is a poet, composer, musician, soki, count, centurion, halfa, jiro, jirchi according to his own interpretation. , aqin, akhun, etc. are glorified.

Large epic schools such as Bulungur, Nurota, Narpai, Kamay, Kurgan, Khorezm, Shahrisabz, Sherabad, Boysun and Chirakchi, which have their own traditions, have been formed in our country since ancient times. In these schools, famous female poets such as Tilla kampir, Sultan kampir, Buvi shaira, Kizsuluv, Ulughoy, Khanimoy sang epics and made a worthy contribution to the development of epic school traditions. In the Surkhan oasis, girls and women also sing epics and play drums. While continuing the traditions of baksheesh passed down from generation to generation, nowadays in Surkhandarya such women baksheesh, along with creativity, continue the tradition of master-apprenticeship typical of our people, train many students to frame our national talents and instill in the hearts of the young generation a sense of love for our motherland. don't come with their contributions. Today, such female bakhshis are active in the Surkhan region and make a worthy contribution to the development of bakhshi traditions. We can mention Zulkhumor Shernazarova and Rahimova Maysara among such women. To glorify the dear and respected female breed in our country, to increase the position and prestige of our sisters in the life of the state and society, to strengthen the spiritual and moral environment in families with their many years of effective work and rich practical experience, In order to properly appreciate our women who make a great contribution to the work of raising our children in the spirit of love for the motherland, respect for national

and universal values, and actively participate in the fundamental reforms that are being carried out in our country, to build a new Uzbekistan and to raise the well-being of our people. A group of women were awarded honorary titles, orders and medals for their efforts.

Shernazarova Zulkhumor Jumaevna was honored with the Order of "Friendship" On September 12-14, 2021, a competition was organized among the philanthropists at the II International Festival of Philanthropy in Nukus. At this festival, Zulkhumor Shernazarova won the "Most Talented Woman Award" nomination. He was born in the farm "Arikh Oshgan" in the Kumkurgan district of the Surkhandarya region. Zulkhumor had an inner aspiration to become a Bakhsh poet from his youth, which motivated him to take up the drum. he looks, his hand is reaching for the drum, his voice is not bad, he has a charm that suits him. He took his first lesson from his brother Amon Bakhshi, and later learned epic poetry and Bakhshi from Shoberdi Bakhshi, Kara Bakhshi and the late Qadir Bakhshi. Zulkhumor sings "Alpomish" taught by his teacher Kara Bakhshi with inner dexterity and delicate feelings. Zulkhumor Bakhshi has won hundreds of prizes until now. With his unique voice and unique voice, he is one of the bakhshis who left an unforgettable mark on the school of bakhshi music in Sherabad and was able to create a new core of this school. Today, he is continuing his teaching activities at the Republican Specialized Bakhshi boarding school in the city of Termiz, and is teaching 28 students in the art of bakhshi. Bakhshi sings dozens of epics and says more than a hundred terms. He sings epics like Alpomish, Gorogli, Nurali, Khondali, Golden Pumpkin, Momogul maston with interest.

Apart from that, Rahimova Maisara Bakhtiyar, daughter of Gulistan neighborhood, Sherabad district, is one of the young artists who has been learning the secrets of bakhshi from her teacher in singing epics. She was born on December 15, 1997. The future Bakhshi, who used to watch and listen to the performances on the y-holidays, danced, played his grandfather's drum with interest for years, and his love for this art was awakened from that.

Although the family members wanted young Bakhshi to study in a direction other than art, his interests and aspirations are on the path of Bakhshi art. While studying Bakhshian terms and epics, he listened more to the works of Shodmon Bakhshi and Shoberdi Bakhshi and tried to perform them. He was 13-14 years old when he started creating. His teacher is Shoberdi Boltayev, the first People's Gift of Uzbekistan. Bakhshi profession is in the blood of ancestors. In the Surkhan oasis, no wedding is complete without bakhshis, whose performances have always been popular with the people. Her goal is to train young girls in the school of bakhshi in the future, because she believes that the performance of female bakhshi will be a special school in the development of this field. A young, talented artist from Surkhandarya, the winner of many competitions, is a participant of the 2019 International Charity Festival held in our country.

Successors of the Sherabad epic school are among the Bakhshis who follow in the footsteps of their teachers and weave epics by themselves. Khushbok Bakhshi, Chori Bakhshi, Kara Bakhshi, Shoberdi Bakhshi, Shodmon Bakhshi, and dozens of their students are growing up among the dynasty of bakhshis who

played seven pink drums and told stories. They create traditional and modern epics and present them to our friendly people. Based on this information, we can easily say that the Surkhan oasis is the land of Bakhshis. The young men of the land with Bakhshi will be brave like Alpomish, and the girls will be as tall as Barchinoy. Collecting these bumpy ways of life, its options and versions, analyzing the new information, collection of epics and terms, which are kept silent in the land of the Bakhshis, in the notebook of the dombira, and printing is our next task.

References and sources

- 1.S.N.Tursunov, G'O'.Ahmedova. Milliy xalq og'zaki ijodida baxshichilik san'atining yuksalishi. Toshkent Tafakkur. 2021 B-101.
- 2.Tursunov S, Paradaev T, Tursunova N, Murtazaev B. O'zbekistonda baxshichilik san'atning shakllanishi va taraqqiyoti tarixi. Toshkent.; 2015. "Tafakkur".B 34.
- 3.Ahmedova, G. O. (2022). The Role of Bakhshi Abdunazar Payanov in the Development of the Art of Baxshi in the Surkhandarya Oasis. American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research, 3(2), 342-346.
- 4.Ahmedova, G. O. (2020). Ational, repertoire, teacher, creation, art, oasis, people, student. Theoretical & Applied Science, (7), 74-77.
- 5.Ikromov, N. M. (2021). The Rule of the Ancient Bactrian Cavalry in the History of the Peoples of Central Asia. Central Asian Journal of Social Sciences and History, 2(10), 111-118.
- 6.Ikromov, N. M. (2021). Kavis'reign in the first territorial statehood of ancient bactria. World Bulletin of Social Sciences, 4(11), 77-81.
- 7.Ikromov, N. M. Is Bactria the Kingdom or the Kavian. EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR). Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR).
- 8.Икромов, Н. М. (2020). Кавийлар тасвирланган бактрия булласи. Взгляд в прошлое, 3(3).
- 9.Икромов Н. Қадимги Бактрия илк худудий давлатчилигида кавийлар хукмронлиги //Общество и инновации. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 10/S. – С. 127-135.
- 10.Ikromov, N. M. (2021). The Rule of the Ancient Bactrian Cavalry in the History of the Peoples of Central Asia. Central Asian journal of social sciences and history, 2(10), 111-118.
- 11.Ra'no, T. U. (2017). Religious and social thoughts of the people of ancient India, Central Asia and Iran. Himalayan and Central Asian Studies, 21(1), 61.
- 12.Urazova, R. T. (2016). Interpretation of the 31st gatha of yasnain" avesta". Himalayan and Central Asian Studies, 20(4), 90.

13. Уразова, Р. Т. (2022, April). Анализ уровней социальных отношений по религиозным источникам (на примере авеста и ригведа). In E Conference Zone (pp. 183-185).
14. Mirzaev, P. D. D. Z. Termez Sayyids, as well as majority of sayyid families of Central Asia, erect the family tree to one of the grandsons of imam Zayn al-abiddin Ali ibn Al-Hussein-Ubaydullah «al-araj»-«Lame». One of the grandsons of Abu Ja'far-Hussein Abu Abdallah has got over in Samarqand, and then in Balkh. His sole son Hasan Abu Muhammad has moved from Balkh to Termez in 865.
15. МИРЗАЕВ, Ж. З. (2021). Термиз шаҳри номининг этимологияси борасида. in Uzbek Conference Publishing Hub (Vol. 1, No. 01, pp. 295-299).
16. Мирзаев, Ж. З., & Саидахматов, Ш. Т. (2021). Марказий Осиёдаги урбанизация жараёнларида термиз шаҳрининг ўрни ва ахамияти. Хабаршысы, 1, 161.
17. Мирзаев, Д. З. (2018). Русское поселение на границе с Афганистаном в личных воспоминаниях. In Частное и общественное в повседневной жизни населения России: история и современность (pp. 290-296).
18. Mirzayev, J. Regional identity formation in central asia from historical perspective.
19. Турдикулов, Ш. Д. (2022). Сурхондарё ономастик сатҳида теотопонимлар. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 1(5), 217-220.
20. Turdikulov, S. D. (2020). Ethnolinguistic features of surkhandarya microtoponyms (on the example of theotoponyms). Theoretical & Applied Science, (4), 81-83.
21. Botyrova, M., & Bozorova, G. (2023). The use of metaphor in fiction. Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture, 3(1 Part 2), 82-89.
22. Botirova, M., & Qayumova, M. (2022). Language Characteristics of Phraseological Units. Procedia of Philosophical and Pedagogical Sciences, 1(1), 80-83.
23. Makhliyo, B. (2022). Linguistic Features of Artistic Similes. Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture, 3(11), 41-46.
24. Qizi, B. M. B., & Sanjarovich, I. S. (2021). Badiiy matnning lingvistik mohiyati. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 1(3), 46-51.
25. Kultayeva, F. (2022, November). Ergonimlarning jahon va o'zbek tilshunosligida o'rganilishi. In E Conference Zone (pp. 131-136).
26. KULTAEVA, Fazilat. "Analysis of ergonomic units at the onomastic level." (2022).

27. Fazilat Kultaeva. (2022). Study of ergonyms in uzbeki linguistics. *World Bulletin of Social Sciences*, 16, 11-14
- Турсунов, С., Пардаев, Т., & Махмадиёрова, Н. (2012). Сурхондарё—этнографик макон.
28. Tursunov, S. (2008). *Toponyms of Surkhandarya region*. T.: Alisher Navoi National Library of Uzbekistan.
29. Tursunov, S., Qobilov, E., Pardaev, T., & Murtazoev, B. (2004). *History of Surkhandarya*. T.: East.
30. Турсунов, С. (2006). ва бошқ. Ўзбекистон тарихи ва маданияти—Сурхондарё этнографияси. Т: Алишер Навоий номидаги Ўзбекистон Миллий кутубхонаси нашриёти, 275, 275.
31. Турсунов, С. (2002). Термизий буюк сиймолари. Т.: Шарқ.
32. Турсунов, С. Н., Чориев, Р. Қ., Муртазоев, Б. Х., & Чўтматов, Ж. О. (2019). *Имом Абу Исо ат-Термизий ва термизлик алломалар.— Т. Yangi nashr*.
33. Турсунов, С. (2010). Хотира-барҳаёт, кадр-мангу. Тошкент: Фан, 10-11.
34. Tursunov, S., Kobilov, E., Murtozoyev, B., & Pidayev, T. (2004). *History of Surkhandarya*. (p. 177). Editorial office of oriental publishing and Printing Company, 2, 1870-1917.
35. Tursunov, S., & Murtazoev, P. (2016). *Scientific thought of Termezians*. T.: Uzbekistan.
36. Tursunov, S., & Rustamova, N. (2021). Professor Mamat Haydarov: Science, Management and Youth School. *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*, 8(7), 602-607.
37. Турсунов, С. Н. (2020). О Сюань-цзане и истории буддизма. *Бюллетень науки и практики*, 6(11), 444-451.
38. Турсунов, С., Умаров, И., Пардаев, Т., Турсунов, А., Холмонова, Ф., & Нарзуллаева, Н. (2017). *Ўзбекистонда топонимик номлар ва уларнинг тарихи*. Термиз: Сурхоннашр, 75.
39. Чориев, Ш. (2017). Соотношение естественного и позитивного в реализации концепта "гостеприимство". *Апробация*, (2), 101-102.

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